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LAW, THE HUMAN PERSON, AND THE PARODY OF ONE NATION

ABSTRACT

The concepts of Law and the Human person are perhaps the most common and complex concepts capable of multiple significations. In one respect, they are common because they are household terms in all times, cultures, and organizations, and people generally seem to understand what they represent. In another respect, their complexity lies in the fact that, by nuanced steps, they could represent distinct layers and/or categories of realities, thereby creating room for prevarication typical of ambiguous concepts. Whether couched in unwritten customs and traditions by which primeval peoples organized their lives, or in standardized penal codes of ‘civilized’ cultures, laws and their enforcement are expedient for meaningful interrelationships of human persons, social order, peaceful co-existence, economic growth, and stability of any society. By sifting out the distinctive disconnect between the practice of law and the general well-being of the Nigerian populace, this essay highlights the basis of social disharmony within the polity. Findings reveal that the causative base of the elite’s penchant for callous abuse of citizens’ rights has direct links with a seemingly warped justice system. The hermeneutic and analytic tools of the qualitative research method are deployed. In the end, the paper concludes that continuing on this trajectory, the languorous parody of political elites that Nigeria will remain ‘one indivisible nation’ is doubtlessly a chimeric dream.

Keywords: Human person, justice system, law, one nation, social order.

INTRODUCTION

Across times and cultures, scholars have conjectured the nature of the primeval state of humans that elicited the formulation and enforcement of laws. In his seminal work, *Leviathan*, which is pivotal to the development of political philosophy, Thomas Hobbes envisions a state of nature wherein individuals, propelled solely by the quest for survival, engage in actions inimical to intersubjective life. Being left vulnerable to the vagaries of harsh environmental

forces, and having no external influence to coerce accountability, there was no limit to human aggressive tendencies. Aggression became a veritable tool for human survival and the conquest of new territories. If we concede to the Darwinian evolutionary refrain that ‘only the fittest survived’, it becomes easy to see how the exhibition of brute force and rude acquisitive tendencies were salutary enterprises in the state of nature.¹ Not surprisingly, Hobbes asseverates that life at this stage of human development was solitary, poor, nasty, brutish, and short,² and required salvaging through the creation of a social contract.

This nasty and brutish ambiance was fertile for the flourishing of such behaviours as would elicit the evolution of cliches as *homo homini lupus* (man is wolf to man); “human cruelty and treachery surpassed all understanding,” etc., which have perdured to this day. But not everyone shares in this gloomy picture. John Locke acknowledges the existence of mutual obligations amongst individuals in the state of nature, even though it lacked governmental structures. He believes the endowment of individuals with the rights to life, liberty, and property is from nature and predates the establishment of civil society. The creation of the commonwealth or civil society was contrived by wilful individuals who sought to leave the state of nature by instituting an impartial power structure capable of arbitrating disputes and redressing injuries.³

Inversely, Jean-Jacques Rousseau conceptualises a peaceful original state of human existence in which there were no desires and man lived as a free, gentle savage.⁴ For him, this pristine, peaceful state of nature was corrupted by human desires and greed, recipes for the current level of human depravity. Civilization or the quest for interdependent life broke the final straw of the state of nature and gave rise to the establishment of a complex regulatory mechanism of formulation, promulgation, and enforcement of laws.

Barring other insignificant idiosyncrasies, it is apposite to note that law originates from the ashes of chaos and disorder to arbitrate human disputes and redress injuries. Laws are promulgated to safeguard the human person within the ambiance of a commonwealth. Without laws, there is no social contract, no commonwealth or civil society, and interdependent life is nearly impossible.

¹ C.N. Ogbujah. “Ethics in Business: In Search of Wholesome Health for Human Society” (Editorial), *Dialogue and Universalism*, 34/1 (2024), 5. <https://doi.org/10.5840/du20243411>

² *Leviathan*, i. xiii. 9.

³ See Munro, A. "State of nature." *Encyclopedia Britannica*, March 28, 2024. <https://www.britannica.com/topic/state-of-nature-political-theory>.

⁴ J.J. Rousseau. 1755. *Discourse on the Origin of Inequality*, as cited in G.H. Sabine & T.L. Thorson. *A History of Political Theory*, New York: The Dryden Press, 1973, 533-7.

This, perhaps, explains why **Rudolph Von Ihering** sees law as “The form of the guarantee of conditions of life of society, assured by the State’s power of constraint.”⁵ The dearth of justice (the rule of law) and ethical values in any polity is a recipe for chaos and anarchy reminiscent of the Hobbesian state of nature.

For long, there seems to be a distinctive disconnect between the practice of law and the general well-being of the Nigerian populace. The nation has been befuddled with myriad crises that have led to individual and collective agitations, militant uprisings, and the formation of ethnic secessionist movements. In this essay, we seek to establish a causative link between the elite’s penchant for callous abuse of citizens’ rights and a seemingly warped justice system. We note that continuing on this trajectory, the torpid parody that Nigeria will remain ‘one indivisible nation’ will doubtlessly be a chimeric dream.

UNMASKING THE NOTION OF LAW

The notions of Law and the Human person are possibly the most ambiguous notions ensconced in multiple significations. In one respect, they are simple and easily understandable notions because they are everyday terms used in all times, cultures, and organizations. In another respect, they are adorned with a garb of complexity due chiefly to the fact that, by nuanced steps, they could represent distinct layers or categories of realities, thereby creating room for prevarication. Consequently, it is important to first delineate these concepts to situate our minds within the context of the discourse.

The notion of law, arguably, arose as a consequence of the escape from the state of nature to civil life – man’s formation of a commonwealth. Its origin dates back to 3000 BC in the traditions of social equality and impartiality of the Ancient Egyptians,⁶ and the subsequent Hammurabi codification in 1760 BC. The moral imperatives of the Old Testament only came around 1280 BC. From the Greek to the Roman empires and down the centuries, law has been adapted to cope with the changing social conditions, and articles that delineate the

⁵ R. V. Ihering, as cited in “Various Definitions of Law,” *toppr*. Accessed 19/4/24 from: <https://www.toppr.com/guides/business-law-cs/introduction-to-law/various-definitions-of-law/#:~:text=Leon%20Duguit%20states%20that%20law,a%20means%20of%20social%20cont,rol>.

⁶ S. Lippert. (11 February 2016). “Egyptian Law, Saite to Roman Periods.” *Oxford Handbooks Online*. (Oxford: Oxford University Press).

relationship of law to political structures are deemed the constitution. The legal systems in force across the world today are split between civil and common laws.

Law can more properly be described as the system of rules that a certain country, community, or group acknowledges as regulating its members' actions and which it may enforce by the imposition of penalties.⁷ Every aspect of this description is instructive since it is believed that for anything whatsoever to qualify as law, it must incorporate some or all of these or their variants, namely: a) a system of rules; b) accepted by a recognizable specific group of people for regulating their lives; and c) enforceable through the imposition of penalties. These are the grand norms without which a contraption cannot qualify as a law. So, whether understood in Friedrich Karl von Savigny's historical sense as "a matter of unconscious and organic growth," or simply seen in Hans Kelsen's rendition as a 'normative science,'⁸ or in Morris Cohen's view as the art of justice,⁹ the overall intent grounding the establishment of law is codified in these trio. Further analyses of Rudolph Von Ihering's already noted definition also reveal three vital dimensions of law, viz: i) law is a means of social control; ii) law is to serve the purposes of the society; and iii) law, by its nature, is coercive.

For the Angelic Doctor (Thomas Aquinas), 'law is a rational ordering of things which concerns the common good that is promulgated by whoever is charged with the care of the community'.¹⁰ Whilst acknowledging these principal qualities of acceptability, coerciveness, etc., that ultimately revolve around "the common good factor", Aquinas charts the way for the source of the power behind the rules that govern people's lives – namely, the *competent authority*. That is, for any rule to have the force of law, it must originate from those who have been charged by the common will to do so.

Among the positivists, Jeremy Bentham's efforts are interpreted as grounding the authority of the Law on the principle of maximizing the 'Happiness of the greatest numbers.'¹¹ Positive laws are not universal, since in

⁷ "Law". Online Oxford Dictionary

⁸ H. Kelsen as cited in "Various Definitions of Law." See also Núñez Vaquero, Álvaro. "Five Models of Legal Science." *Revus. Journal for Constitutional Theory and Philosophy of Law*, 19 (10 June 2013), 53–81.

⁹ M. L. Cohen. *Law: the Art of Justice*. Beaux Arts Editions. (Westport, Conn.: Hugh Lauter Levin Associates, 1992).

¹⁰ T. Aquinas. *Summa Theologica*. 1a2ae, 90.4. Trans. by J. G. Dawson. (Oxford: Basil Blackwell, 1954).

¹¹ J. Bentham. *An Introduction to the Principles of Morals and Legislation*. (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1789).

reality, they originate from customs that define specific people. So, whether the emphasis is on the acceptability of the law, or the authority of its maker(s), or on its utility, every law which is enforceable through human sanctions is made by man, to be obeyed by all and for the wellbeing of everyone. In this sense, even the divine source of the Judeo-Christian legal principles given in the Pentateuch is mediated by a human instrument – Moses. In John 1:17-18 we read:

The law indeed was given through Moses; grace and truth came through Jesus Christ. No one has ever seen God. It is God the only Son, who is close to the Father’s heart, who has made him known.

Hence, positivists insist on the human origin and practical usefulness of laws.

Perhaps, there isn’t a much more forcefully couched description than that from Jean Jacques Rousseau thus:

But what, after all, is a law? [...] When I say that the object of laws is always general, I mean that law considers subjects en masse and actions in the abstract, and never a particular person or action. [...] On this view, we at once see that it can no longer be asked whose business it is to make laws, since they are acts of the general will; nor whether the prince is above the law, since he is a member of the State; nor whether the law can be unjust, since no one is unjust to himself; nor how we can be both free and subject to the laws, since they are but registers of our wills. [...] Laws are, properly speaking, only the conditions of civil association. The people, being subject to the laws, ought to be their author: the conditions of the society ought to be regulated solely by those who come together to form it.¹²

Laws are thus just rules of conduct freely made by humans for the guidance of everyone’s life, contrived out of human need for justice and order in societies and organizations.

As originating from the will or common consciousness of the people, either directly or indirectly, laws are indispensable for the smooth ordering of societies and institutions. A society without laws, and perhaps an effective means of enforcing the laws, would be like the animal kingdom where ‘might is right’, and only the fittest of animals will survive; it would be a chaotic, dysfunctional state reminiscent of Hobbesian ‘state of nature’ where life was ‘solitary, poor,

¹² J. J. Rousseau. (1762). *The Social Contract*. Trans. by G. D. H. Cole. Book II: Chapter 6 (Law). Assessed on 18/10/2014 from:

<http://www.marxists.org/reference/subject/economics/rousseau/social-contract/ch02.htm#006>

nasty, brutish and short'. This may seem an extreme position given that some scholars like Locke would argue that even in the state of nature, humans were imbued with a sense of mutual obligations, or that there are people who are not selfish, and as such, would still live happily with others without laws. This, if it occurs, would be in awfully rare circumstances given that we live in a world of scarce resources, and are constantly faced with the challenge of eking out a living. Indeed, as Hobbes would say, it might be cogent to kill someone in self-defence before you get killed, that is, if you want to carry on living. So, in reality, it is only the rule of law and the threat of punishment that keep humans in check.¹³ Law shapes politics, economics, history and society in various ways and also serves as a mediator of relations between people.

DYNAMICS OF THE HUMAN PERSON

The notion of the human person, by nuanced steps, has undergone mutations that have given rise to prevarications. This is expected since, owing to prevalent intellectual cultures, each epoch or subgroup tries to couch its idea of personhood in a language understandable to the people of the times. The ancient and medieval times were dominated by the cosmocentric and theocentric frames of reference, respectively. And in these periods, the conceptualization of man showed some sort of subordinacy to either the world or God. But with modernity initiated by the Cartesian *cogito*, the philosophic atmosphere was charged with anthropocentric humanism that viewed man as the lynchpin of the universe.¹⁴

In the ancient Western world, the idea of the human person was alien to their thoughts, even though the reality it signified – man, was present. The reflections of Socrates, Plato, Aristotle, the Cynics and Skeptics, etc., were, at best, predispositions of the various conceptions of what constitutes the human person. Indeed, it was Christianity that later brought to light its decisive structure. As Baptista Mondin asseverates, the singularity of the person, unique and unrepeatable, and as a matter of fact, the substantial equality in dignity of every human being is a truth carried, affirmed, and diffused by Christianity.¹⁵ The occasion for its formulation came with the theological disputes regarding the mysteries of the Trinity and Incarnation. In an attempt to apply a term to the Father, Son, and Spirit without dissolving their individuality, and at the same time not falling into the danger of making them three divinities, Augustine used

¹³ Some of the ideas relating to the meaning of law presented here had earlier been expressed in a separate forum. See. Ogbujah, C.N. "Ethics, Law and Justice in Achebe's *Things Fall Apart*."

¹⁴ C.N. Ogbujah. *The Idea of Personhood*. (Enugu: Snaap Press Ltd., 2006), 3-4.

¹⁵ B. Mondin. *Philosophical Anthropology*, (Rome: Urbaniana University Press, 1985), 244.

the term *hypostasis* (Greek) or *persona* (Latin) — person, which meant something singular and individual'.¹⁶ And by way of inversion, he applied this term to man: *singulis quisque homo [...] una persona est* — every single man ... is a person.¹⁷

Perhaps, the first most adequate definition of the human person was given by Boethius (480-524A.D). In *Contra Eutichen et Nestorium*, he writes: *persona est rationalis naturae individua substantia* — person is an individual substance of a rational nature.¹⁸ Here, Boethius weaves together a sublime compendium that was to lead much of modern and contemporary research on the human person. Person is not only a single individuality, nor simply nature, nor simply substance. It is not even a union of these elements that can belong to a stone or a merely sentient being like a goat. Person is a union of these with the sublime quality of 'rationality.' This view was later taken up and somewhat modified by Thomas Aquinas by substituting the Boethian terms 'individual' and 'substance' with the term 'subsistent'. For him, *persona est subsistens distinctum in natura rationalis* — person is a distinct subsistent in a rational nature.¹⁹

In reality, both Boethius and Aquinas hinged the other qualities of the human person to that of rationality, and together, they formed the basis of the ontological concept of personhood. Aquinas further claims there is no distinction between man and person by harping on the tri-stadial development of man from the vegetative to the animal, and finally to the sublime rational stage. The rational seed is already planted in man from conception. What other humanising factors do is to enhance, complement, and help consolidate what is already given naturally. Hence, person for Aquinas, signifies what is most perfect in all nature.²⁰

Whilst this ontological tradition is of great achievement for initiating the inquiry into the specific meaning of personhood, it is somewhat ambiguous by limiting the constituent qualities to rationality and subsistence. This leaves room for the inclusion of higher animals like Dolphins or Chimps whose brains are complex enough to be called rational, as persons. A resolution, however, came in the modern era when philosophy, following Cartesian dualism, shifted its focus from metaphysics to epistemology. By identifying the self with the mind — *res*

¹⁶ Augustine. *De Trinitate* (On the Trinity) VII, 6, 11; see C.N. Ogbujah. *The Idea of Personhood*, 7.

¹⁷ Augustine. *De Trinitate*, XV, 6, 11.

¹⁸ Boethius. *Contra Eutichen et Nestorium* (Against Eutichen and Nestorium), C.4 cited in Ogbujah, C.N. *The Idea of Personhood*, 7-8.

¹⁹ T. Aquinas. *Summa Theologia*, 1, q 29, a. 3

²⁰ T. Aquinas. *Summa Theologia*, 1, q 23, a. 3

cogitans (the thinking thing) whose essence is consciousness, Descartes insisted that the human person must be seen not in relation to the autonomy of being, but in relation to self-consciousness. The ‘I’ in *Cogito ergo sum* consists in self-consciousness, or put differently, the self-consciousness authenticates the ‘I’.²¹

This Cartesian transposition of the person from the ontological to the psychological opened the way to a series of expansions and contractions by subsequent philosophers like Frederick Nietzsche, David Hume, Sigmund Freud, Jean-Paul Sartre, Gilbert Ryle, Peter Strawson, and Bernard Williams. Nonetheless, their contributions have met with a series of objections in the contemporary era by scholars like Jacques Maritain, Emmanuel Mounier, Gabriel Marcel, Maurice Nedoncelle, James Reichmann, Martin Buber, and Carol Wojtyla who play up the dialogical (intersubjective) perspective over and against the ontological or psychological ones. **Mounier**, for instance, makes a case against all his predecessors who construe a person as a simple psychological, subjective, and individualistic phenomenon. Person, for him, is a presence directed toward the world and other persons, a presence that shares with others through communication. In his auspicious volume *Personalism*, he notes:

Common opinion notwithstanding, the fundamental nature of the person is not originality, nor self-knowledge, nor individual affirmation. It lies not in separation but in communication.²²

A person, therefore, is by nature a communicable being. To struggle for the person, thus, means for Mounier, to struggle against all forms of alienation that threaten the fabrics of interpersonal relationships on which the being or reality of the person is hinged.²³

While accepting Aquinas’ view of the human person, **Karol Wojtyla** (Pope St. John Paul II) also examined human existence from a phenomenological perspective. This method led him to the conclusion that it is in the act of self-determination that a unique personal being can be fashioned and developed. In his 1976 Harvard Lecture, he said: “I possess self not so much through self-

²¹ R. Descartes. *Discourse on Methods and Meditations*. (London: Penguin Books Ltd. 1968), 53, 54.

²² E. Mounier. *Personalism*. (Indiana: University Of Notre Dame Press, 1952), 17.

²³ C. Ogbujah & C. Opara. *The Idea of Human Personhood in Nigeria: Implications for National Development*. (Port Harcourt: Pearl Publishers, 2014), 3.

consciousness as through self-determination.”²⁴ For Wojtyla, it is through the act of self-determination that an individual experiences oneself as a person; and it is only through self-determined actions directed toward others for their benefit that the acting person becomes more fully himself as a person.

Besides these, there is yet another concept projected by Batista Mondin, and seen as a somewhat synthesis of prevalent notions. This perspective trumps descriptive over essential definitions, and adds the quality of transcendence to those of ‘subsistence’, ‘consciousness’, and ‘communication’. For Mondin, “Man is not simply an ex-sistent (Heidegger), or a co-existent (Buber), and not even just a subsistent (Boethius), but he is a transcendent.”²⁵ This eclectic view ends up describing the person as a subsistent gifted with self-consciousness, communication, and self-transcendence, and since every living human being is endowed with these qualities, every human being is a person.²⁶ and must be respected as such. Undoubtedly, these conceptions ground the Western penchant for personal autonomy and regard for individual rights that have shaped the trajectories of their social lives.

In Africa, exemplified in Igbo tradition, however, there appears a subtle divergence from this Western meaning-content. Here, the idea of the person is, for the most part, tied to the idea of the community. The community here is considered a convivial organic structure in which there are intimate, personal interactions among its members, and from which they derive their existence and sustenance. This view has diversely been espoused by scholars like Chinua Achebe, Theophilus Okere, Ifeanyi Menkiti, John Mbiti, Panteleon Iroegbu, D.I. Nwoga, Boniface Nwigwe, Columbus Ogbujah, among others. Okere, for instance, notes that “The self is a congenitally communitarian self, incapable of being, existing and really unthinkable – except in the complex of relations of the community.”²⁷ This communitarian personhood was poignantly captured by Menkiti as he avers:

Persons become persons only after a process of incorporation.
Without incorporation into this or that community, individuals are

²⁴ K. Wojtyla. (1976 Harvard Lectures), in M.T. Clark. *Persons and Personality Identity*. Assessed from: <https://www.bu.edu/wcp/Papers/Pper/PperClar.htm>

²⁵ B. Mondin. *Philosophical Anthropology*, 256.

²⁶ B. Mondin. *Philosophical Anthropology*, 256-257.

²⁷ T. Okere. (Ed.) *Identity And Change*. (Washington, D. C.: Paideia Publishers, 1996), 160.

considered to be mere danglers to whom the description ‘person’ does not fully apply.²⁸

Menkiti brought out the processual nature of the person in the African thought-pattern. In his line of thought, personhood is something that has to be achieved. It is not given simply because one is born of a human seed.

It is crucial, nonetheless, to note that the emphasis on the primacy of the community for the attainment of personhood in Igbo thought pattern is not oblivious to the reality that the community can only act on an ontologically constituted species. An ontologically constituted species may have attained manhood as the case may be, but not personhood. Personhood is something that is structured by societal underpinnings. Hence, through an hermeneutics of extant literature and oral interviews, Ogbujah avers that “a person rather is a human being (with all human capacities) who has consciously realized himself through social roles and functions in the society.”²⁹ There is no doubt that this processual conception, in certain respects, has had ominous consequences for the people.

UNDERSTANDING THE NEXUS BETWEEN LAW AND THE HUMAN PERSON

Ordinarily, a cursory look at the independent significations of these various concepts should suffice for this nexus. However, a deeper analysis does demonstrate the inadequacy of relying on hermeneutics grounded merely on face value. More so, reliance on face value tends to obfuscate the possibility of engaging in the three-fold process of dissection, conjecture, and hypothetical reconstruction. Our aim, thus, is to segment aspects of the law and the human person, so as to make fitting conjectures about their primordial accord.

Many are wont to revel in the cliché that “the law is made for man, not man for the law,” i.e., the law is an instrument for the flourishing of the human person; a tool for the attainment of human goals. Hence, when a law ceases to serve its purpose, it is either amended or repealed. New laws are constantly enacted to meet the demands of changing realities. While it is neither possible to enact laws for every conceivable human situation, nor to enforce rules for all actual infractions, the ingenious discoveries of men and women of the new age elicit tremendous work in the area of jurisprudence. The aims, among others, are

²⁸ I. A. Menkiti. “Person And Community In African Traditional Thought”, in *African Philosophy, An Introduction*. 172.

²⁹ C.N. Ogbujah. *The Idea of Personhood*, 187.

not just to safeguard people's inventive products from piracy, but to protect the entire human species from self-destruct. In other words, a proper hermeneutics of the cliché "the law is made for man not man for the law" forecloses every attempt at instrumentalising the human person for whatever reason. The human person is prior to, and superior to the law both at the ontic and ontological levels. Phenomenologically, their connexion is a subordinated relationship wherein the human person trumps the law.

A sequel to, and as it were, an affirmation of this subordinated relationship can be gleaned from the prior analyses of the notion of the human person, especially from the African perspective. Whilst the Western egocentric view harps on the ontological primacy of rationality, the Igbo socio-centric view emphasizes the ontological primacy of the organic structure of relations between individuals within the community. The human person is naturally oriented toward others and must have relationships with them. Using the Igbo saying: *mmadu anaghi agba ka ugba* – a human being does not fall like a bolt by some inexplicable explosive mechanism, Okere maintains that there is no big bang that throws a human being from nowhere into the world. "Every one has a source, a link, a belongingness Everyone comes into the world belonging and relating."³⁰ Belongingness of the human person is generative of society, which provides the ambiance for its realisation, whilst the formation of society, in turn, elicits the making of laws. Without belongingness, there is no society, and without society, there are no laws. Law is subordinate to and serves the needs of human persons enmeshed in community (societal) life.

The idea of the human person resonates with the idea of human dignity, equality, freedom of choice, and basic other rights that originate from the natural law, which are open to those with a complex capacity for reasoning. To conceive or respect someone as a person is to see him/her as an entity that has dignity, that can steer the course of their life through personal decisions, and with whom we share equal patrimony.³¹ Without freedom of choice, for instance, actions cannot be imputed to their agents for praise or blame, and without imputability, agents are mere puns, whose conducts are not reckoned more than that of purely sentient beings. For one to be a person, he must have an unqualified claim to some social and economic advantages, which are central to his leading a dignified life. These are provided for by the laws. Hence, the positive laws of nation-states, by

³⁰ T. Okere. (Ed.) *Identity And Change*, 159.

³¹ R. E. Goodin, 'The Political Theories of Choice and Dignity'; *American Philosophical Quarterly*, Vol. 18, 1981, 95.

conforming to the provisions/expectations of the natural law, aim to provide protection to the human person.

A corollary to this is the emphasis on the rule of law. The rule of law ensures that public agents do not operate pursuant to the promotion of individual whims and caprices; that all are treated equally within the ambit of the law; and that no one is above the law. In jurisprudence, law in itself neither commands respect/obedience, nor evinces good governance. In the hands of unscrupulous agents, it can become an instrument of terror. The rule of law is directly integral to the implementation of rights, associated with economic development, and necessary for democracy and good governance. It is the rule of law that facilitates geopolitical stability and societal transformation. Being, as Aquinas indicates, the most perfect in all realities, the human person can only flourish in a society operating under the rule of law. Anything to the contrary is a recipe for social disorder, which recently has bestridden Rivers State, and indeed, the Nigerian nation.

THE PARODY OF ONE NATION

In the introductory paragraph to the general provisions of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 as amended, we read in part:

WE THE PEOPLE of the Federal Republic of Nigeria:
 HAVING firmly and solemnly resolved: TO LIVE in unity and
 harmony as one indivisible and indissoluble sovereign Nation
 ... DO HEREBY MAKE AND GIVE TO OURSELVES the
 following Constitution.³²

Then, shortly afterward in Chapter 1, art.2.-(1) we read: “Nigeria is one indivisible and indissoluble sovereign state to be known by the name of the Federal Republic of Nigeria.”³³ This, perhaps, is the ground norm that tele-guides the utterances of political elites on discussions concerning the continued viability of a Nigerian state. Often, when people clamour for a reasonable resolution to the lingering crises arising from the constituent ethnic groups’ conduct as strange bedfellows, those who benefit from the dysfunctional system, especially past and present leaders, always take refuge in this languid platitude. President Obasanjo was especially adept in parodying this to all who cared to listen. In his speech at the National Summit organised by NLC in 2012, President Jonathan berated those seeking the disintegration of the country and dubbed them “lazy politicians

³² Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999, No. 24 *LL 15*

³³ Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999, No. 24 *LL 15*

seeking to be kings in tiny islands.”³⁴ He claimed that Nigeria will not be divided under any pretext. Even though Jonathan instituted a Sovereign National Conference to discuss the way forward for the beleaguered nation, he limited their scope of interaction, noting *inter alia* that the conference “shall discuss any subject matter, except the indivisibility and indissolubility of Nigeria as a nation.”³⁵ This is like telling kids to eat all candies except chocolates.

The apparent incongruity of claims to indivisibility, and the veiled authoritarian attempt at demonising its adversaries as ‘detractors and enemies of the state’ have been identified by Jidefor Adibe, as acts of desperation by ‘opportunists who pretend to be more patriotic than the rest of us by masking their personal, ethnic and other chauvinistic interests with false nationalism.’³⁶ For long, political elites masked their inordinate ambition of superintending large empires under the guise of nationalism. Azikiwe, Gowon, Murtala, Obasanjo, Buhari, Jonathan, Tinubu, and all their acolytes have demonstrated this penchant. Blinded by the largesse of the vastly unaccounted petrodollar, and buoyed by the prospect of filling up political offices with their kin and cronies, they turn a blind eye to the plight of the generality of the people. They instigate ethnic profiling, nepotism, and religious bigotry, which pitch constituent nations at daggers-draw; they are not interested in taming non-state actors that kill, maim, and occupy the ancestral lands of others to further their ethnic and religious biases.

Since the dawn of independence, Nigeria has been a theatre of war. Although the war of attrition that nearly exterminated the Biafran enclave purportedly ended on January 15, 1970, the reverberations are still felt today more than half a century after, in discriminations on government appointments, in injustices on the allocation of resources and infrastructural development, and in turning a blind eye to security menace by religious and tribal bigots. The three major ethnic groups seem to be at daggers drawn, with members fighting for secession. In the end, the entire political space has become a theatre of war, with violent “Boko Haram” attacks, despicably brazen activities of kidnappers, ritual murderers, armed robbers, the unconscionable looting of the public treasury,

³⁴ “Nigeria’s unity is non-negotiable – Jonathan.” *Vanguard* 21 September 2012, <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2012/09/nigerias-unity-is-non-negotiable-jonathan/>

³⁵ “Update: Nigerian government releases details of National Conference”, *Premium Times*, January 30, 2014, <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/news/154259-breaking-news-nigerian-government-announces-modalities-national-conference.html>

³⁶ J. Adibe. “The mantra, ‘Nigerian unity is not negotiable’, is pseudo-nationalism”, *Linkedin*, July 20, 2017, <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/mantra-nigerian-unity-negotiable-pseudo-nationalism-jidefor-adibe>

intimidation, and extrajudicial killings by security agents, vicious communal classes, and the rape of justice by the judiciary. We live in a country where staying alive the next hour is a luxury, yet people are more concerned with the size. Like Tolu Ogunlesi, we ask: Is “unity” a more important ideal than self-determination, human dignity, freedom of choice, and a meaningful existence? What value does unity have in a failing country where all that many have for food is suffering, for drink is the water of poverty, and for security is perpetual fear? Must we protect unity at all costs, even if it entails handing over pain and lack from generation to generation? What exactly does “unity” mean? And should anyone who asks for a reconsideration of blind loyalty to a failing nation be deemed guilty of being a traitor?³⁷

Ironically, the real traitors are those who cling to this sinking ship for personalized and selfish gains; those who feed fat on the blood of a wider empire. Contrary to Jonathan’s diatribe on opposing views, those who seek the peaceful dissolution of this enclave might be the real messiahs. What Jonathan and his co-travellers often sidestep conveniently is that the mantra of indissolubility as enshrined in the Constitution is followed immediately by the caveat that this constitution is provided ‘for the purpose of promoting good governance and the welfare of all persons on the principle of Freedom, Equality, and Justice.’³⁸ They pay lip service to Section 14(2) (b) of the Constitution which declares that the security and welfare of the people shall be the primary purpose of government. Where is the government when politicians and other public office holders loot the common treasury dry with no consequences? Where is government when Boko Haram, terrorist Herdsmen and kidnappers brazenly maim, rape and kill citizens and occupy their territories? Where is the government when the impunity of electoral umpires is deodorized and certified by the Judiciary? It is clear none of those parodying this listless cliché seems bordered by the underlying motif of staying together. A government that prioritizes a mantra over the well-being of its citizens, and fails to convince them that the benefits of remaining together far outweigh the benefits of going it alone, is a complete failure. What should be non-negotiable is the right of the people to self-determination and to freely and

³⁷ T. Ogunlesi. “Is the unity of Nigeria truly non-negotiable?” *Premium Times*, May 19, 2014, <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/opinion/161053-unity-nigeria-truly-non-negotiable-tolu-ogunlesi.html?tztc=1>). See also, P. A. Adebisi. “Who says the unity of Nigeria is not negotiable?” March 20, 2014, <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2014/03/says-unity-nigeria-negotiable/>

³⁸ Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999, No. 24 *LL 15*

peacefully decide their future. This parody is indeed a classic case of Caesar fiddling while the city of Rome burns.

MURDER IN THE CATHEDRAL (THE BASTARDIZATION OF THE JUSTICE SYSTEM)

In 1935, the verse drama by T.S. Eliot – *Murder in the Cathedral* was first performed. The play displays the assassination of Archbishop Thomas Becket in Canterbury Cathedral by the Knights at the behest of his supposed friend and ally, King Henry II. Drawing heavily from the account of an eyewitness to the event – Edward Grim, Eliot paints a vivid picture of the dialectic of power and suffering, friendship and betrayal. Being appointed by Henry II as the Chancellor and later Archbishop of Canterbury, Becket least anticipated that his friend would plot his downfall. The histrionic import of the event reached a crescendo when the Knights (supposed defenders of the church) cut off his head on December 19, 1170, in the Cathedral.

The symbolism of this to the harrowing state of the nation is pervasive. Nigeria is a rich nation blessed with abundant human and natural resources. Yet, she is adjudged the poverty capital of the world. Her resources have been mismanaged and pillaged by the supposed custodians of the people's patrimony. And to suppress the call for accountability, these enemies of the people have corrupted the last hope of the common man – the judiciary.

As an indispensable arm of the tripod that constitutes the governing structure of democratic societies, the judiciary is saddled with the onerous job of adjudicating between conflicting parties within the ambit of the law. In particular, its duty is to interpret laws based on the Constitution, to administer justice, and to ensure that laws are impartially complied with. Apparently, these duties are the basic reasons, in Lockean rendition, for the creation of the commonwealth – “instituting an impartial power structure capable of arbitrating disputes and redressing injuries.” Whilst we acknowledge the invaluable works of both the executive and legislative arms of government in a democracy, no one can contest the centrality of the judiciary to good governance. It serves to bridge between executive rascality and legislative overreach and is structured to prevent abuse of power and safeguard freedom for all. This, perhaps, explains why it is regarded as the last hope of the common man.

Sadly, the Nigerian situation has defied every logic, and the last bastion of hope has become the straw that constantly breaks the camel's back. Some are wont to excuse the Justices on the grounds that the executive often deploys its

Federal might to intimidate and cajole them into submission by arbitrarily removing non-pliant ones – as we saw in the callous dismissal of Walter Onnoghen – the Chief justice of the Supreme Court weeks before the 2019 elections; or by denying/withholding their statutory allocations. Being forced to depend on the benevolence of the Executive, the Judiciary loses its bite as a co-equal branch of government and merely subsists as an appendage to be dispensed with at will. Having lapsed into totalitarianism, it becomes easier for the Executive to flout competent court orders without consequences. Ogbujah avers:

In any nation, where the legislature is being manipulated by the executive, and the legislative seal is used to instigate anti-people policies; where the judiciary is used to upend the will of the masses in elections, leadership has slid from democracy to tyranny.³⁹

Although this ‘excuse theory’ sounds compelling, it is disingenuous to absolve the judiciary of complicity, as in many cases, they are active agents in upending the will of the people. Rather than ascribing judicial failures to executive overreach, the deadly monster in the room is corruption.

Judicial corruption eats into the fabric of human civility with the potential to destroy democratic cultures. It begins with the appointment of incompetent, or unscrupulous / politically exposed justices to run the judiciary, and culminates with seeing the election petitions’ tribunals as cash-cows. The consequences are seen in the granting of frivolous *ex parte* orders, in unconscionable adjournments and delay of justice, in taking refuge under judicial technicalities to subvert justice, in jettisoning judicial precedence to establish conflicting norms, and in adopting positions that show outright miscarriage of justice. We see this in the inexplicable dismissal of Imo State governor – Emeka Ihedioha from office by the Supreme Court in a manner that dumbfounds even legal luminaries to date; the irreconcilable imbroglio of the Supreme and Appeal Court judgments on the governor and members of the Plateau State house of assembly; and in suppressing evidence through technicalities to affirm the election of President Tinubu in the 2023 elections. The most recent are the bizarre rulings regarding the Rivers’ political imbroglio, where the Supreme Court waded into a ‘Defection’ case that was yet to be determined at the Federal High Court - in an apparent move to arm-twist the judges at the lower court. The cost of these

³⁹ C.N. Ogbujah. “Equality, Equity and Justice in Resource Distribution in Nigeria,” *Filosofia Theoretica: Journal of African Philosophy, Culture and Religions*, Vol. 10. No. 2(2021), 138.

questionable judgments to society is bad leadership, leading to poverty, an increase in crime and insecurity, preventable suffering, and death. Thus, although there are countless instances of miscarriages in our commutative justice system, these political cases are foregrounded to underscore the importance of leadership to the flourishing of a nation. For as the holy writ declares in Proverbs 29:2: “When the righteous are in authority, the people rejoice: but when the wicked are in power, the people mourn.”

Judicial corruption in Nigeria is tantamount to murder in the cathedral. As in Eliot’s drama, these crimes are committed in the hallowed temples of justice by those charged with safeguarding the common patrimony. They reinforce corruption and acts of impunity of political officeholders, and trump their oft-ill-conceived and selfish policies over the well-being of the masses. The enormity of these is couched in the audacious refrain: “If you don’t like it, go to court.” This refrain is from the inglorious head of the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC), Mahmood Yakubu, who oversaw what is adjudged the most fraudulent election in Nigeria’s history. With the declaration of Tinubu as president-elect in the wee hours of March 1, 2023, despite complaints of massive irregularities, Mahmood cut off the head of democratic participation in Nigeria. “Go to court” has become a catchphrase to symbolize people’s propriety in laying claims to illegality; a refrain to despondency since there are artisans ready and willing to murder justice in the cathedral. “Go to court” has become a slogan to symbolize the failure of the justice system.

PRIORITIZATION OF LAW TO THE HUMAN PERSON.

In the foregoing expose, we have demonstrated the primacy of the human person over the law both at the ontic and ontological levels. We have seen that whether understood as a subsistent gifted with self-consciousness, communication, and self-transcendence (Western views), or a being that has consciously realized himself through social roles and functions in society (Igbo [African] view), the human person predates the law. The parlous situation of humans in the state of nature necessitated the creation of *Leviathan* (Hobbes) or the Commonwealth (Locke), and the commonwealth could only function with positive laws. When we say that “law is made for man, not man for the law,” the implication is that law is an instrument for the flourishing of the human person; a tool for the attainment of human goals.

In Nigeria, however, the reverse is the case as law is prioritized over the welfare of human beings, and has become a tool of subjugation. At the front, this is orchestrated by the sham we call the Constitution. The northern oligarchs

knew, as Aristotle would say, that “laws must be adapted to the constitution,”⁴⁰ and so, through a military fiat foisted on the masses, a Constitution that is twisted in favour of the North and the practice of Islam. Since the return to civil rule in 1999, political actors have exploited its loopholes to perpetuate corruption and dehumanizing acts against the masses, and under its shield, Northern legislators have successfully scurried every proposed meaningful amendment.⁴¹ This is why, in some circumstances, cows are more protected than humans, and the marauding herders could pillage people’s farmlands without consequences.

At another front, the harassment and suppression are orchestrated by the interpreters of the law at the temple of justice. This is what we had referred to as “murder in the cathedral.” Besides relying on ‘technicalities’ to delay or deny justice, besides issuing procured judgements and conflicting claims based on political patronage, besides bare-faced judicial robbery in maliciously twisting the rules in the middle of the game to favour cronies, there are also issues of structural violence arising from structural injustice. Structural injustice entails the use of obnoxious laws in causing harm to the human person. The violence thereof is a consequence of the deliberate implementation of policies and structures that cause human suffering, harm, and death. A society that prioritizes law over the well-being of its citizens often glosses over such indirect and subtle forms of violence that emanate from social structures, which make it difficult for people to meet their basic needs.

Whilst all the previously outlined infractions constitute massive subversion of the rule of law, and can still be challenged (even if with no hope of redress) at a certain level, acts that perpetrate structural injustices cannot be challenged in any competent court as they are within the bounds of the law. Remedy can only come through a revocation or an amendment to the law. Unfortunately, for power brokers that prioritise law over the human person, executing the letters of the law is much more important than attending to the spirit of the law or the needs of the people.

POST MORTEM

In the foregoing, we have attempted to weave together the intricate link between the law, the human person, and the desire for a commonwealth. Being dissatisfied with brute life in the state of nature, the human person sought the

⁴⁰ Aristotle. *The Politics*, trans. by Thomas Sinclair. (Penguin: Harmondsworth, 1962), III, 11, 1282a 8-14.

⁴¹ Ogbujah, C.N. “Equality, Equity and Justice...”, 137.

commonwealth. To promote intersubjective and interdependent life within the commonwealth, the law was needed. In terms of priority, the human person trumps the law. Law is posterior to and subordinate to the needs of the human person. Law is made for man, and not man for the law. The primary motif of law is the overall well-being of humans in society.

Unenforced laws are of no consequence to human well-being and societal growth. This is why the rule of law constitutes the bedrock for flourishing in liberal democracies. The rule of law is a durable system of institutions and community commitment that delivers accountability, just law, open government, and accessible and impartial justice. It is the foundation for accountability and respect of human rights, and correlates to higher economic growth, greater peace, more education, improved health outcomes, and unity.⁴² No doubt, its nonexistence inversely correlates with the abuse of power, acts that dehumanize persons and groups, lower economic growth, a poor healthcare system, a politicized educational system, protracted conflicts, and disunity that have characterized the Nigerian nation today. In his phenomenological analyses, Pope St. John Paul II stood against anything that dehumanizes the human person and maintained that it is in the act of self-determination that a unique personal being can be fashioned.⁴³ Hence, to build a thriving commonwealth under the rule of law, individuals must be allowed the right to self-determination; otherwise, the elite's parody of 'one indivisible nation', no matter how loudly orchestrated, would remain a chimera.

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⁴² See World Justice Project. *WJP Rule of Law Index, 2023*, <https://worldjusticeproject.org/about-us/overview/what-rule-law>

⁴³K. Wojtyła. (1976 Harvard Lectures), in M.T. Clark. *Persons and Personality Identity*.